

ON THE SMARANDACHE PRIME ADDITIVE COMPLEMENT SEQUENCE

Maohua Le

Department of Mathematics, Zhanjiang Normal College
Zhanjiang, Guangdong, P.R.China.

Abstract. Let k be an arbitrary large positive integer. In this paper we prove that the Smarandache prime additive complement sequences includes the decreasing sequence $k, k - 1, \dots, 1, 0$.

For any positive integer n , let $p(n)$ be the smallest prime which does not excess n . Further let $d(n) = p(n) - n$. Then

the sequence $D = \{d(n)\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ is called the Smarandache prime additive complement sequence. Smarandache asked that if it is possible to as large as we want but finite decreasing sequence $k, k - 1, \dots, 1, 0$ included in D ? Moreover, he conjectured that the answer is negative (see [1, Notion 46]). However, we shall give a positive answer for Smarandache's questions. In this paper we prove the following result:

Theorem. For an arbitrary large positive integer k , D includes the decreasing sequence $k, k - 1, \dots, 1, 0$.

Proof. Let $n = (k + 1)! + 1$. Since $2, 3, \dots, k + 1$ are proper divisors of $(k + 1)!$, then all numbers $n + 1, n + 2, \dots, n + k$ are composite numbers. It implies that $d(n) \geq k$. Therefore,

D includes the decreasing sequence $k, k-1, \dots, 1, 0$. The theorem is proved.

Reference

1. Dumitrescu and Seleacu, Some Notions and Questions
In Number Theory, Erhus Univ. Press, Glendale, 1994